

PARENTAL AND PERINATAL FACTORS AND ASD: A ROMANIAN EXPLORATORY RESEARCH

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Autism spectrum disorder is a complex neurodevelopmental condition. High and low blood pressure, parental age, premature delivery, low weight birth, cesarean section, birth complications and neonatal intensive care were described in scientific literature as potential risk factors for ASD.

Material and method: 102 children born between 2009 and 2014 were included in the studied group. We analyzed gender, types of diagnostic, parental age and level of education, birth order of ASD child, types of child delivery, and obstetrical complications during birth.

Results: 49% of mothers were over 31 years old when they gave birth to children in our study group. 36.27% of fathers were over 36 years old at childbirth, and 16.67% of them were even over 41 years old. 69 children (67.6%) are the firstborn and 79.42% of children suffered birth complications.

Further researches and data analysis are needed to understand the risk factors for ASD.

Keywords: autism, parental age, perinatal risk factors.

INTRODUCTION

Autism spectrum disorder (ASD) is a complex neurodevelopmental condition. Based on the 5th edition of Diagnostic Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-5), specific diagnostic criteria for childhood autism include social skills and communication deficit associated with restrictive and repetitive behaviors, interests, or activities (American Psychiatric Association, 2013).

Epidemiological surveys of the prevalence of pervasive developmental disorders (PDDs), including autistic disorder (AD) worldwide show there is a high variation in prevalence proportions that ranged from a low 30.0/10 000 to a high of 116.1/10 000,

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with a median rate of 61.9/10 000 in Europe. In a global view, it was estimated a median of 17/10 000 for AD and 62/10 000 for all PDDs combined. This is currently the best estimate for the global mean prevalence of PDDs available and it translates into one child out of 160 with a PDD (Elsabbagh et al. 2012).

The main cause of ASD is genetic. However, in search of specific genes responsible for ASD it became obvious that there are numerous candidate genes on many chromosomes, and only rare cases of ASD can be related to specific genes. The spectrum of symptoms and the extreme complexity in the developmental and associated medical conditions within ASD do not necessarily mean a single etiology. Several hypotheses concerning the pathogenesis have been proposed, including the interaction of environmental factors and various genetic predispositions. Autism may represent a heterogeneous entity, where in some cases genetic factors, and in other cases environmental factors, may predispose to the disorder.

A recent study suggests that genetic factors account for only 35–40% of the cases, the rest 60–65% is likely due to many environmental factors, such as prenatal, perinatal and postnatal factors (Froelich-Santino et al. 2014). Maternal infections, gestational diabetes, high and low blood pressure, parental age, premature delivery, low weight birth, low Apgar score at 1 or 5 minute after birth, cesarean section, drugs used by mother during pregnancy, birth complications and neonatal intensive care unit treatment were described in scientific literature as potential risk factors for ASD.

According to many studies, adverse intrauterine environment resulting from maternal bacterial and viral infections during pregnancy is a significant factor for ASD. Hadjkacem et al. (2016) found that the occurrence of maternal infection was higher among ASD children when compared to controls (12%, respectively 3.9%) (Hadjkacem et al. 2016).

Another risk factor associated with disturbed fetal growth and increased rate of a variety of pregnancy complications is gestational diabetes. It also affects fine and gross motor development and increases the rate of learning difficulties and attention deficit disorder, a common comorbid behavioral problem in ASD (Ornoy et al. 2001).

Recent studies have linked advanced maternal and paternal age to increased risk for ASDs (Parner et al. 2012, Sandin et al. 2012).

Theories advocating the association between parental age and increased risk for ASDs include the potential for more genetic mutations in the gametes of older fathers and mothers, as well as a less favorable in utero environment in older mothers, with more obstetrical complications such as low birth weight, prematurity, and cerebral hypoxia (Parner et al. 2012). The interrelationship between autism and obstetric complications may be confounded by the influence of birth order. That is, obstetric complications may be more frequent in firstborn children-in families with 2 children, or in late born children-in families with at least 3 or 4 children (Glasson et al. 2004).

Fetal hypoxia is one of the manifestations of fetal distress and has been reported to induce conditions such as placental abruption, threatened premature delivery, emergency cesarean section, forceps delivery, spontaneous abortion, and varying degrees of cerebral damage (Gomes et al. 2015, Gardener et al. 2011).

Glasson et al. (2004) found that induced labor is associated with the risk for ASD. The interpretation of this finding remains challenging because the indications for induction of labor are multiple. Bilder et al. (2009) have shown that both breech presentation and cesarean delivery are associated with ASD, but the association with cesarean delivery was lost after excluding the children in which breech presentation was an indication for the operation.

In one study from Finland, ASD was associated with cesarean delivery but not with breech presentation. In the final model, only planned cesarean delivery (an operation scheduled before the labor starts), but not emergency/urgent cesarean, remained significant (Polo-Kantola et al. 2014).

Another birth factor associated with ASD is preterm delivery. Johnson et al. (2010) studied children who were born at <26 weeks of gestation and compared them with term-born classmates at 11 years of age. In this study, 16/201 (8%) of the preterm children were diagnosed with ASD, and none of the classmates received an ASD diagnosis.

Kuzniewicz et al. (2014) found that among infants <34 weeks gestational age, ventilation and intracranial hemorrhage were more frequent and associated with ASD. Also, ASD was 3 times more prevalent in infants with a gestational age smaller than 27 weeks compared with the term infants. Furthermore, each week of shorter gestation was associated with an increased risk of ASD.

The present study aims to explore some of the parental and obstetrical risk factors for ASD presented in the literature on a Romanian lot of ASD children to point out the importance of these factors in the etiology of autism.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The studied group includes 102 children born between 2009 and 2014, of which 19 girls (18.63%) and 83 boys (81.37%).

Children were diagnosed with autism by psychiatrists from the public health system in our country. Their medical diagnosis was also confirmed by specific psychological tests that measured the abilities and deficiencies of the subjects in several areas of development (ADOS 2).

The research was conducted between 2016–2017 in a therapy center in Bucharest. The research team was composed of one psychologist, anthropologist, physician, and special education professionals who implemented a questionnaire with personal data of parents and children, data on pregnancy, birth and first year of life, medical diagnoses, and specific psychological tests (ASRS, ADOS 2).

For this paper, we analyze gender, types of diagnostic, parental age and level of education, birth order of ASD child, types of child delivery (full-term, preterm, natural birth, cesarean section birth), and obstetrical complications during birth.

RESULTS

Gender. The studied group consists of 19 girls (18.63%) and 83 boys (81.37%), which verifies the data from the literature on the sex ratio regarding the incidence of autism in children (1/4).

Diagnostic. Depending on the year of diagnosis and the vision of DSM in that period, as well as the severity of the condition, diagnoses range from autism spectrum disorder (ASD) (39.22% of children), atypical autism (23.53% of children), autism infantile (29.41% of children) and PDD-NOS (7.84% of children).

Parental age. Figure 1 shows the distribution of parental age at the moment of birth. It indicates that the rate of advanced age (≥ 35 years) among ASD children's parents at the moment of birth is high (13.7 % of mothers and 36.2% of fathers).

Fig. 1. Parental age at childbirth.

The average age at childbirth is 30.60 years for the mother and 34.07 years for the father. 35.29% of mothers gave birth between the ages of 31 and 35.

49% of mothers were over 31 years old when they gave birth to children in our study group.

36.27% of fathers were over 36 years old at childbirth, and 16.67% of them were even over 41 years old.

The literature shows that the advanced age of the parents at the time of conception, especially of the father, is associated with an increased risk of ASD and the results of our study confirm these data.

Educational level. 70.59% of fathers and 60.78% of mothers involved in this study had a higher education levels (more than a high school education). (Table 1)

Table 1

Educational level of parents

Educational level	Mother (N)	Father (N)	Mother (%)	Father (%)
Gymnasium	3	2	2.94	1.96
High school	37	28	36.27	27.45
Higher education	62	72	60.78	70.59

Birth order of ASD child. In the studied group (102 children with ASD), 69 children (67.6%) are the firstborn. 31 children (30.39%) are second born and only two are the third (Figure 2).

Birth order of ASD child

Fig. 2. Birth order of ASD children.

Birth types. 33.33% of the children in our study group were born prematurely.

Of these, 11 were born naturally (32.35%), the remaining 23 (67.65%) were born by cesarean section.

Of the 68 full-term babies, only 19 were born naturally (27.94%), the remaining 72.06% were born by cesarean section (Figure 3).

Fig. 3. Birth types.

To understand better the correlation between maternal age and the type of child delivery, we represent the data in Figure 4. As you can see, at every age interval, the cesarean delivery in this group of study is higher than 50%. 75% of child delivery in 31–35 years interval were cesarean and only 25% were natural birth. Over 50% of the births needed a cesarean intervention in the entire studied lot, and for the mothers who delivered the children after the age of 30 years, the C-section was needed in over 70% of the cases.

Fig. 4. Child delivery types on mothers age.

Birth complications. 79.42% of children suffered birth complications such as acute fetal stress, hypoxia, green amniotic fluids, prematurity, induced labor, difficult labor, and emergency cesarean intervention.

DISCUSSION

Our findings confirmed the sex ratio of 1 girl to 4 boys affected by ASD.

The concern about the increasing rate of the advanced age at childbirth of ASD children worldwide is confirmed by our findings. The average age at childbirth is 30.60 years for the mother. Recent research in literature found a direct association between the advanced age of mother or father and the ASD and/or other diseases. Also, few researchers suggested that birth order is a risk factor for autism, especially in the case of the firstborn or the last born. And in our study, 67.65% of studied children were firstborn. There is a subject of further research if a combined factor, such as an advanced age of mother and/or father at the moment of conception of the first child is not an increasing risk factor for the contemporary population. The higher level of parents' education in this study group (found in some other studies in scientific literature, too) is linked with the advanced age of parents at the firstborn, because they need more time to finalize their studies, to build a career, start a family. Of course, this hypothesis needs more research and discussions in the future, alongside a detailed analysis of many other risk factors and data collected in the original research.

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